

Data Citation Practices among CESSDA Service Providers Monitoring Report 2024-2025

Description

This report examines data citation practices among CESSDA Service Providers, guided by the recommendations outlined in the *CESSDA Data Citation Guide* for data repositories. For each recommendation, current practices are described and complemented by reflections and suggestions aimed at enhancing their implementation. The report provides concrete proposals to assist Service Providers in adopting the recommendations and to guide the future activities of the CESSDA Data Citation Working Group in its efforts to strengthen data citation practices within CESSDA and the broader social science research community. Data collection was conducted between May and September 2024, with a follow-up review in April and May 2025 to support Recommendations 2 and 4, acknowledging the rapid evolution of data citation practices.

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Introduction

In 2024, the CESSDA Data Citation Working Group gathered information on data citation practices, guidance, and support from CESSDA service providers (SPs) in both member and partner countries. This report aims to summarise the findings and identify current strengths and weaknesses in these practices.

Data was collected using a Google Sheet, where participants' responses were openly accessible to all invited contributors (see the questions in the Appendix). The goal of the questionnaire was to assess whether CESSDA SPs' practices align with the CESSDA Recommendations on Data Citation for data repositories (Bornatici et al., 2025)¹, which the Working Group had developed earlier as part of its mandate. Accordingly, the questions were structured to evaluate alignment with each recommendation.

Data collection occurred between 21 May and 16 September 2024. The initial call for participation was sent via the Service Providers Forum's Basecamp on 21 May, followed by several reminders in Basecamp and through email, particularly targeting those member countries' SPs that had yet to respond. Despite these reminders, 5 member SPs did not participate, resulting in 17 member SPs providing information, along with contributions from 2 partner SPs. Notably, 18 out of the 19 respondent SPs provided their answers before mid-June.

As data citation practices are a current focus and subject to continuous improvement, some information may have already changed. To mitigate this issue, supplementary information on the SPs' data citation practices was incorporated. Given the potential for varied interpretation of the survey questions by SPs, this additional information was obtained by reviewing the citation details available on the SPs' landing pages, accessed via the links they provided in their survey responses. This review was conducted in April and May 2025, in support of Recommendation 2 on metadata provision and Recommendation 4 on the components of citation examples.

This report analyses the responses provided by SPs in relation to each recommendation, highlighting both common practices and notable differences among SPs. Based on these observations, it offers a series of suggestions and reflections aimed at enhancing current practices. The findings are intended to support the development of targeted measures to strengthen data citation practices within CESSDA and across the wider data repository community.

¹ Also available as a website under the name of [CESSDA Data Citation Guide](#).

The results by recommendation

Recommendation 1 – Request data to be cited

Results from the survey

The questionnaire started by asking SPs whether they request that data accessed through their services be cited ("Does your SP request data to be cited?"). All 19 respondent SPs indicated that they require citation of data accessed through their services.

They reported several methods used to inform users of this requirement. It is common practice to communicate this expectation within the reuse conditions associated with datasets, either through general terms of use provided on the SP's main website or data-sharing platform, or through dataset-specific metadata, particularly in the case of datasets with restricted access.

For such restricted-access datasets, a frequently used approach is to display the citation request on the dataset's landing page, often accompanied by a data citation example. In some cases, the data citation request is also provided through a dedicated terms of use tab within the metadata. Pop-up notifications or links to the terms of use can also be provided during the download process.

For datasets distributed under open access licences (e.g., CC-BY, CC0), users are often neither requested nor reminded to cite data before download, with the exception of SPs using Dataverse.

Among the 19 respondent SPs, 9 use the Dataverse platform. It is therefore worth explaining how Dataverse manages data citation. For data with restricted access or those licensed under open access terms that include an attribution requirement (e.g., CC-BY), Dataverse includes built-in data citation information in a pop-up window that appears when downloading data. This encourages citation as a community norm and as part of good scientific practice, though it does not require it: *"Our Community Norms as well as good scientific practices expect that proper credit is given via citation. Please use the data citation above, generated by the Dataverse"*. While this pop-up is not presented for datasets released under public domain licences (e.g., CC0), the 'Terms' tab in the dataset metadata remains available in all cases and provides similar guidance. Of the 9 Dataverse-using SPs, 8 complement these platform features by adding explicit "Terms of Use" in the metadata, clearly requesting citation when data are reused, particularly for datasets with restricted access. One SP relies solely on Dataverse's general norms to encourage citation.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

The findings reveal several good practices currently employed by SPs to promote proper data citation. A key strength lies in the inclusion of data citation requirements directly alongside citation examples, particularly on dataset landing pages. This pairing helps to contextualise the example and reinforces the expectation that data should be cited. Another positive practice observed is the use of reminders at the point of data download. These reminders serve as a final prompt to users and help embed citation as a standard part of the data reuse workflow. Both of these approaches reflect a growing awareness among SPs of their role in fostering responsible data usage and should be strengthened and adopted more widely.

Despite these good practices, there remain several areas where improvements could enhance consistency and clarity in citation requirements. First, some SPs appear to conflate the provision of a citation example with a formal requirement to cite. This suggests a lack of clarity in how citation expectations are communicated. While citation examples are indeed important for improving citation accuracy (see also Recommendation 4), they do not, on their own, constitute a formal request. SPs should therefore ensure that they explicitly state a requirement to cite data. In cases where data are released under public domain licences (e.g., CC0), and legal requirements to cite do not apply, SPs are still encouraged to strongly recommend citation as a matter of good scholarly practice.

Second, although multiple approaches are used to communicate data citation requirements to users, the requirement should ideally also be included in the metadata that may be picked up by automated processes, such as rights or licensing fields. Placing this metadata alongside the data citation itself would further enhance users' awareness of the requirement.

Third, while many SPs display data citation requests within dataset metadata, such requirements are less commonly provided during the download process. SPs are therefore encouraged to introduce explicit reminders at the point of download to reinforce the importance of data citation. This is especially relevant for public domain datasets, where users may not otherwise perceive a legal obligation to cite.

Finally, to enhance citation awareness and compliance, SPs could consider implementing additional measures for both restricted and openly available data. These may include requiring users to acknowledge their intention to cite the data before download, and/or embedding within each download package a brief guidance that outlines why and how to cite data appropriately, together with the requirement (or recommendation for public domain licenses) to cite the data. Such practices would

contribute to a more consistent citation culture within data reuse, irrespective of the access conditions under which the data are made available.

Recommendation 2 – Provide all six core data citation components

Results from the survey

The CESSDA's recommendations for data citation (Bornatici et al., 2025) identify six core components of a data citation: (1) authors, (2) title, (3) publication year, (4) version, (5) publisher and (6) persistent identifier (PID) of the dataset. The second recommendation for data repositories stipulates that SPs should include these core elements within their metadata. This ensures that users have access to the necessary information to produce a complete and accurate citation when referencing the data in their publications.

Regarding this second recommendation, we were first interested in the six core components provided as specific metadata fields related to the datasets (and hence not the information contained in the data citation example, which was the concern of recommendation 4). This assessment was done in April and May 2025 for all 19 respondent SPs who originally responded to the questionnaire.

1. **Authors:** Nearly all respondent SPs (18 out of 19) include a specific metadata field for data authors, with the remaining SP incorporating this information within the citation example. This field may be labelled in various ways, such as authors, producers, creators, contributors, depositors and may refer to individuals and/or institutions. Some SPs use several metadata fields to show different types of author roles. However, not all types of authors were included in the citation examples. In such cases, the citation example was necessary to determine which authors should be cited.
2. **Title:** All 19 respondent SPs provide information about the title of the dataset in the metadata associated with the dataset.
3. **Year of publication:** Approximately three-quarters of SPs (14) include information on the publication year, often specifying the full publication date. Among the 5 SPs that do not provide this as a distinct metadata field, 4 include the year of publication in the citation example. For 1 SP this information could not be found.
4. **Version:** 15 SPs provide the version of the published dataset. While the version is a core component of the data citation, the way this information is presented varies across SPs, which is the focus of the next section related to Recommendation 3.
5. **Data publisher:** This was the least commonly included core component as a specific metadata field, with only 12 SPs (63%) providing such a field. However,

all SPs include this information in the citation example. A range of terms is used to label this field across SPs, including publisher, provider, and distributor.

6. **Persistent identifier:** A PID was available as a specific metadata field in 16 SPs (84%). Where it was not present in the metadata, it was included in the data citation example (or vice versa), with the exception of 1 SP that does not yet provide PIDs. As for the types of PIDs used, most SPs provide a DOI, while Dataverse users also include a UNF. A minority of SPs make use of handles and URNs.

Second, we also checked whether SPs provided three additional components that are sometimes required by bibliographic styles or publishers: (1) accession or data number, (2) resource type, and (3) place of publication. Apart from the data number (available in 14 SPs; 74%), these components were rarely provided as metadata. Resource type was absent across all SPs, while place of publication was present in only 4 SPs (21%). Moreover, the data number itself could often be difficult to locate and identify.

Third, in addition to examining the SPs, the metadata fields supported by the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) were also examined. The CDC supports all core components, except for the version. Regarding the additional components, it supports the data number. As the CDC harvests metadata from SPs, the availability of specific metadata fields in individual study pages depends directly on the extent to which those fields are available in the harvested metadata.

Overall, we observed notable variation in the display of both core and additional components as metadata. While core components are generally provided, they can at times be difficult to identify, for example when multiple author roles are listed (author, PI, responsible institution) or when both publishers and providers are included). In some cases, these elements were not preceded by a clear label and were dispersed across multiple webpages. For all these reasons, the provision of a citation example is of critical importance.

Finally, in addition to assessing the availability of the core components, SPs were also asked whether they control their quality and whether they provide a persistent identifier (PID) prior to the publication of datasets. All 19 respondent SPs reported that they undertake quality control of the core metadata components provided by data depositors, especially the dataset title. Some indicated that specific rules were applied to titles (e.g., exclusion of dates), while others reported that suggested changes were discussed and implemented in collaboration with the authors.

Regarding PIDs, the provision of a persistent identifier prior to publication can foster data citation practices among data authors themselves (i.e., data depositors). This is particularly important because data authors often delay publication of their data until

after the release of their own research publications. Yet, data authors still require a way to cite their own data. SPs were therefore also asked whether they are able to reserve a PID before publication. One SP reported that it does not offer the possibility to reserve a PID, and one left the question unanswered. The remaining 17 SPs either allocate a PID to the dataset in advance of the full metadata publication or provide a PID on request if researchers need it before the data release.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

The review confirms several good practices: most core components of data citation are already provided by SPs, quality control measures – particularly for dataset titles – are in place, and PIDs can be provided prior to data publication. These represent important strengths.

At the same time, further improvements are recommended. The version remains a key gap and should be systematically included, given its importance for distinguishing data citations from other forms of publication, and for replicating analysis and verifying results. Most importantly, CESSDA Data Citation Catalogue should support this field.

Quality control could also be extended to authorship, ensuring that all relevant roles in the national context are retained in the metadata while clarifying, in collaboration with data depositors, which should appear in the citation. This may require a review of metadata field labelling, including the possible creation of a dedicated field for data authors (citation). This should be further discussed with the CESSDA Controlled Vocabularies Working Group.

Finally, the reservation of PIDs is a good practice that promotes both data sharing and data citation. A key question, however, is whether metadata should always be made publicly available (without data access) when a PID is reserved or assigned. Doing so would ensure that references to the data consistently resolve to metadata, as is recommended for unavailable data (e.g., via tombstone pages). In addition, providing data authors not only with a preliminary PID but also with a citation example containing all core components would guide them in citing their own data accurately.

Recommendation 3 – Provide data versioning and access information

Results from the survey

To assess compliance with the third recommendation for data repositories, SPs were asked how they inform users about dataset versioning and whether access is provided to older versions of metadata and published datasets. Clearly identifying dataset

versions is essential for ensuring complete and accurate data citation. Moreover, maintaining access to specific versions enables replication of research findings by allowing users to analyse the exact data used in the original study. Where access to earlier versions is not feasible, providing detailed documentation of changes between versions can still support transparency and reproducibility by enabling users to understand how the dataset has evolved over time and to assess the implications of these changes for their own analyses.

First, the SPs were asked how information about dataset versions and related changes is provided to their users. Most SPs report that they version their data, except for 2 that do not version their data at all. These two SPs generate their Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) through DataCite, where versioning is required, resulting in all references generated from their DOI defaulting to version 1.

When monitoring the data citation practices among the SPs that answered the survey, it's found that all but 3 SPs include version information in the metadata on their landing pages. One SP provides only the date of the latest version without a version number and omits version details in the citation example, while 2 include version information in their citation examples.

Four SPs don't consistently include version information in their citation examples, though they do offer version or edition information in their metadata. For instance, one SP only includes version information in citation examples if the version number exceeds 1. Another SP, using Dataverse, has different versioning for data files compared to the overall study itself, leading to inconsistencies between citation example versions and data file versions.

Although most Service Providers version their data in some way, it varies whether they provide information about version changes through a change log or version history. Among the 9 SPs using Dataverse, a versioning tab can be used to display the information on changes made from one version to another. There are similar solutions used by SPs using different software. Some of the SPs have a notes page or a section in the study metadata where version information is given, while others keep an internal version log, where version information can be provided to users if requested.

When it comes to the question of whether or not the SP provides access to metadata of all published versions of a dataset, 11 SPs answered that they do provide metadata for earlier versions of a dataset. To come to this number needed a bit of interpretation. In some cases the user must have the PID that takes them directly to the earlier version. In other cases all versions of metadata can be accessed via the latest version. 6 SPs do not give access to earlier versions of metadata.

The last question concerning recommendation 3 was “Does your SP provide access to older published versions of a dataset and how is it done?” 14 SPs answered that they can provide access to older versions of the datasets. How it is done varies. Several SPs mention that the user must contact their service desk (or such). Permission of the data owner may be needed as well. In the case of Dataverse, its features include the possibility to provide access to older versions of the datasets. Some point out that if the data has been removed, they cannot be accessed and only metadata would be accessible at the landing page. 5 SPs do not provide access to older versions of the datasets.

The SPs were finally asked how information about deprecated datasets is provided to the users. There are 11 clear cases of SPs which create a tombstone type of landing page for datasets that are no longer available. The rest describe their practice in such ways that it is not easy to interpret whether it is possible to provide a landing page currently. A strict interpretation would be that 5 SPs do not keep landing pages alive after removing a dataset. Thus, in these cases it is not clear where the PID would resolve. One of the SPs reports plans of transitioning to Dataverse, after which there will be a tombstone per removed dataset. One SP maintains that they keep all data, and thus there would not be a need for this feature. One mentions that there are no such cases yet, where they would have needed it. As the same SP uses Dataverse, they have the feature available, if the need arises.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

Although most SPs version their data and offer version logs, not all do. To enhance transparency and reproducibility, repositories should increase efforts when it comes to versioning, version change logs and access to earlier versions of datasets. While many SPs offer "tombstone pages" for unavailable datasets to maintain persistent identifier links to metadata, this should be a practice among all SPs, as ensuring metadata access for unavailable datasets is crucial for accurate referencing. Several SPs also provide access to earlier versions of datasets, but how this information is conveyed to users varies. As versions of datasets might be removed due to copyright or GDPR issues, it is not always possible for repositories to grant access to earlier versions.

Recommendation 4 – Provide data citation suggestions including all six core components

Results from the survey

As of spring 2025, all 19 respondent SPs provided a data citation example for each dataset. In one case, however, the citation was particularly difficult to interpret, as it

was spread across multiple lines and did not follow any recognised bibliographic style. In most other cases, the examples resembled APA style or were explicitly labelled as APA but did not always conform to the latest APA 7th edition guidelines or its specific requirements for data citation.²

Among the 19 respondent SPs, 14 included all six core components in their citation examples (nine of which use the Dataverse platform):

1. **Authors:** All 19 respondent SPs included the data authors in their citation examples. In one SP, the “data authors” mentioned in the citation example were referred to as “data producers” in the metadata, although “data authors” were also listed in the metadata.
2. **Title:** All 19 respondent SPs also provide a title in the citation example.
3. **Year of publication:** The publication year (or date) was missing in one case.
4. **Version:** The version was absent from the citation examples of four SPs. In some cases, the version component was omitted from the citation example despite versioning information being available in the metadata. The version could also be embedded in the DOI (e.g., through version-based suffixes) but not included as a distinct component. In two SPs, the version was present in the citation but not specified in the metadata. One SP provided a version number only for subsequent releases, not for the first one.
5. **Data publisher:** All 19 respondent SPs provided a publisher in the citation example. However, in some cases the publisher named was not the data repository itself (i.e., the SP), but a research-performing organisation (RPO). In one SP, both the SP (listed as the “data distributor” in the metadata) and an RPO (listed as the “data publisher” in the metadata) were mentioned.
6. **Persistent identifier:** Two SPs did not provide a PID in their citation examples, instead offering only a URL to the dataset’s landing page. Among those that did include a PID, the majority used a DOI, one used a URN, and one used a Handle. Dataverse users additionally included a Universal Numerical Fingerprint (UNF).

Fewer SPs incorporated additional components into their data citation examples. The resource type and the dataset number – both mandatory elements under APA 7th edition style – were included by nine and seven SPs respectively. Three SPs included the place of publication.

The SPs were also asked whether the data citation example is provided in multiple citation styles (e.g., APA, Chicago, MLA) to facilitate citation for users. Most SPs (16) offer the citation example in only one reference style, typically following an APA-like format. Three SPs provide examples in three to four citation styles. The most

² <https://apastyle.apa.org/style-grammar-guidelines/references/examples/data-set-references>

frequently used among these are APA (3), Harvard (3), and Vancouver (3), with Chicago (1) and Oxford (1) mentioned less often.

In addition, 13 SPs reported addressing this need by enabling users to export citations in any desired style via reference management software – a feature notably supported by the Dataverse platform (see also Recommendation 5). Among these, two SPs combine both approaches, offering export functionality as well as citation examples in multiple styles.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

The survey findings reveal that, while all respondent SPs provide citation examples, inconsistencies remain in their completeness, clarity, and alignment with the recommendation. Several SPs already offer structured citation examples, including the six core components, but further improvement is needed to ensure that all core components are consistently applied across SPs. Looking ahead, outreach efforts should emphasise how structured and comprehensive data citations enhance dataset discoverability, reuse, and impact. In parallel, clearer guidance is required on implementing citation practices that align with both CESSDA and broader community standards. Finally, providing SPs with template-based citation suggestions, harmonised with CESSDA recommendations, would offer a practical tool to identify and correct incomplete or inconsistent citation formats.

Recommendation 5 – Facilitate data citation for authors through export and download of metadata for reference management software

Results from the survey

For Recommendation 5, the SPs were asked whether they provide tools that allow the automatic import of data citation components into reference management software (e.g., EndNote, Mendeley, Zotero). As mentioned above, 13 SPs reported offering such tools, typically through download links for bibliographic reference file formats, while six SPs do not. Of those that do, nine use Dataverse, which supports EndNote XML, RIS, and BibTeX formats. Among the four SPs not using Dataverse, bibliographic files are provided in RIS and BibTeX formats, with one also offering EndNote XML.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

As 7 of 19 SPs do not provide functionality for importing data citation components to reference management software, raising awareness about the benefits of such features is strongly advisable.

Initiatives to support SPs could be to recommend or develop automated citation generation tools that could streamline adoption of the CESSDA recommendations. Several SPs still need to provide support for specific citation styles and formats to support different disciplinary requirements.

There are ready-made web components making the delivery of common reference manager file formats easy to implement in a web-based data repository or catalogue, such as Citation.js (Willighagen, 2019). The implementation of such web components will ensure good interoperability with reference management tools. It will also enable generation of dynamic in-page data citation examples (recommendation #4) based on common methods for expressing citation style definitions, such as CSL (Citation Style Language) (Zelle, 2015). When developing citation tools, SPs should at a minimum provide downloadable citation metadata in the common RIS reference file format for a specific dataset.

As an alternative to importing downloaded reference manager files, data citation core components may also be extracted and imported into reference management software through direct interaction with persistent identifier infrastructures, such as DOIs and their embedded metadata. SPs that are not able to provide tools for importing citation components could present alternative means of generating citations. This may include presenting information on how to generate data citations with reference management software using import functionality that accepts PIDs as input, as well as providing guidance on the usage of other online citation generators that obtain metadata from PIDs.

Taking PID-centered citation workflows into account, it is especially important to ensure that the metadata supplied by SPs to generate and maintain PIDs include all the core components of a data citation, and that the metadata stored in the PID systems are likewise kept updated to reflect the core components after any relevant changes have occurred. When using PID-centered workflows, this is the actual information that users extract to generate a citation. Studies examining data citation mechanics indicate that misconfigured metadata exports or negligence to synchronise updated metadata contents with PID kernel metadata caused by the repositories themselves are some of the most common sources of error in data citation, besides design weaknesses in reference manager file formats and software (Vrouwenvelder et al, 2025).

Recommendation 6 – Make citation information and other publication metadata accessible through generic structured metadata files

Results from the survey

For recommendation 6, the SPs were asked if they provide metadata in a standardised and machine-actionable linked data format. Among the 19 respondent SPs, 16 provide metadata in a standardised and machine-actionable linked data format. However, which formats they provide, varies.

A total of 11 SPs reported that they provide metadata in the DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) standard. Two SPs provide metadata in the DDI-Lifecycle standard, eight in the DDI-Codebook standard (one in both DDI Lifecycle and Codebook standards). The remaining two SPs did not specify which DDI metadata standard they use. Metadata in the Dublin Core standard was mentioned by 4 SPs, and one SP mentions that they provide metadata in the DCAT-AP standard. 7 SPs report that their metadata meets the standards of DataCite's Metadata Schema. It can be assumed that most SPs minting DOIs are using DataCite and should at least provide the mandatory components of the DataCite Metadata Schema. Export of their metadata to OpenAIRE is supported by 4 SPs, while 6 SPs mention providing Schema.org metadata, i.e. through JSON-LD (JSON for Linked Data). Eight SPs mention that their metadata is available in an implementation-specific custom JSON (JavaScript Object Notation)-format.

Ten SPs reported that they made metadata available through OAI-PMH (The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting), while 4 SPs made metadata available through OAI-ORE (Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange). Finally, one SP mentions that their metadata is openly available through a GraphQL API.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

Many SPs report compliance with specialised and domain-specific metadata standards such as DDI. However, adoption of the DCAT Application Profile for Data Portals in Europe (DCAT-AP) remains low. Although DCAT-AP may not offer the same level of domain-specific granularity as DDI, its use remains important for ensuring compliance with EU data interoperability frameworks.

To fully align with the FAIR principles, it is also essential to advocate for the complementary adoption of generic metadata schemas. While specialised domain-specific and cross-domain metadata standards such as DDI and DCAT-AP play a critical role in providing rich, structured documentation of datasets, the

complementary use of more generic schemas like Schema.org is also very valuable – especially for enhancing discoverability and web interoperability.

Many SPs have already implemented Schema.org metadata, which supports broader visibility by enabling generic search engines and general-purpose platforms to index and interpret citation metadata along with other basic information about the data contents. A baseline implementation suggested for SPs is Schema.org JSON-LD embedded in dataset landing pages and/or as separate metadata files (Payne & Verhey, 2022).

Basic information about the dataset and where it is further described may also be provided in the HTTP header contents of the landing page itself using methods commonly referred to as signposting. The availability of header-based metadata will ensure that global actors and infrastructures may access and interpret information about the dataset at the very core of the web infrastructure delivering it, and SPs should consider implementation of the FAIR Signposting Profile for scholarly objects (Sompel et al, 2023). This will provide useful machine-readable information, such as the expression of formal *described-by* relations which refer to relevant metadata files, including metadata on the core components of a data citation.

For metadata to be harvested by CESSDA's Data Catalogue (CDC), SPs need to provide metadata in a DDI format (DDI 2.5 Codebook standard/DDI Lifecycle) that is compliant with the latest version of CESSDA's Metadata Model through an OAI-PMH endpoint (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, n.d. Adding a new endpoint). It is therefore recommended that all SPs provide metadata in a DDI format through an OAI-PMH endpoint that can be harvested by the CDC. As the CDC is interoperable with external providers, such as OpenAIRE, GoTriple and B2Find, metadata can be shared more widely if included in the catalogue (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, 21.06.2022, CESSDA Data Catalogue – FAIR enough?).

Although CESSDA's Data Catalogue harvests and disseminates metadata from the SPs, the landing pages for each dataset in CDC do not provide information regarding data citation. As many of the core components of a data citation already are harvested by CDC, CDC could promote data citation by, for instance, offering data citation examples and reference manager file downloads for each dataset in the same manner as recommended for data repositories/SPs.

Recommendation 7 – Make data publications and relations to other entities machine-actionable through rich metadata and PIDs

Results from the survey

The question “Does your SP provide metadata to express relationships between the

data publications and other entities, using machine-actionable PIDs?" received responses from 18 SPs out of 19 SPs. A total of 12 SPs reported that they did provide metadata to express relationships between data publications and other entities, using machine-actionable PIDs, while 6 SPs did not. Of the 12 SPs that did provide metadata to express relationships between data publications and other entities, 10 mentioned that they provide ORCID for authors. Only three SPs mentioned that they provide ROR IDs for research organisations, in addition to other IDs such as ISNI, LCNA, VIAF and GND. One of these SPs also mentioned DAI, Web of Science ResearcherID and Scopus Author ID. Several SPs mentioned the expression of relations to other DOIs, which are crucial for uniquely identifying and linking data publications to related scholarly articles. Several SPs also mentioned using PIDs to define relationships to other digital objects, having the relation types expressed as formal metadata statements using DataCite Event Data.

The question "Does your SP provide hierarchical relations among datasets and subsets (such as dataset versions)?" was answered by 19 SPs. A total of 11 SPs report that they do not provide hierarchical relations among the datasets and subsets. The remaining eight SPs provide different kinds of hierarchical relations between datasets and subsets. Several SPs report that they provide some sort of relation between data collections, series, projects and the datasets.

It is sometimes unclear how these relations are implemented. Some mention that the connections are provided by linking URLs. Some SPs provide PIDs to both datasets and files within a dataset, while others provide or will provide concept/canonical DOI's that encloses all related versions of the dataset with all respective DOI's. Several SPs employ the Dataverse platform to organize datasets into thematic collections, where each dataset is equipped with a versions tab that helps track updates and revisions effectively. Distinct DOIs are assigned to different versions of datasets, and these DOIs are linked to related studies. Some providers utilise the concept of a "data project" as a core organizational unit, allowing for the hierarchical integration of multiple datasets.

In addition, Dataverse software enables individual files within datasets to be assigned their own persistent identifiers (PIDs), with version control facilitated by appending version numbers to these PIDs, thereby enhancing traceability. A cumulative DOI approach is also implemented by some providers for all versions of a dataset, which is particularly useful for datasets that are updated periodically; this approach includes managing relationships to datasets published elsewhere through DataCite Event metadata.

There were 19 SPs who answered the question "Does your SP facilitate the inclusion of subsets PIDs in the data citation?" Most SPs do not facilitate the inclusion of subsets PIDs in the data citation. Only two SPs report that they provide citations for subsets of data or individual files within a dataset. One of these two SPs allows for citations that

include the correct DOI for subsets of data available through a section of their online system and the other noted that they create Dataverse collections for datasets that have subsets, which helps in organizing and potentially citing these subsets. One SP reports that they will provide individual DOI-suffixes to files within a dataset in the future, when they will migrate their repository to Dataverse.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

Many challenges appear when interpreting research information on scholarly objects such as datasets and their relations to other entities, especially when automated workflows are used. Limited or ambiguous data author, institutional affiliation and funding metadata pose problems limiting the possibility for research data to be cited, connected to other scholarly outputs and to be included in scientometric analyses. Clear relations to other relevant actors and phenomena in the research ecosystem will make a data citation more valuable. ORCID and ROR ID are at present likely the most important PIDs for expressing such relations, ensuring that data author, institutional affiliation and funding metadata stays unambiguous and verifiable in citation, indexing and reuse of data.

Several SPs report that they support ORCID to express relations to data authors and other individuals. To make maximum use of the ORCID infrastructure, SPs may implement search integrations using the ORCID API to assist users with lookup and input of ORCIDs and other metadata related to an individual. Data authors should be encouraged to make their ORCID entries public and readable by global infrastructures.

The reported use of ROR ID to express unambiguous affiliations and relations to RPOs, funders and research infrastructures is not as widespread among SPs. Implementation of ROR ID in the metadata models and submission processes of repositories along with guidance for depositors on how to use it to express affiliations is highly recommended. For example, a search integration may be implemented using the ROR API to provide controlled input of official names and ROR IDs in sections where users may input metadata on organisations. Likewise, SPs may provide guidance for RPOs and funders on how to create new ROR entries for their respective organisations or suggest updates to existing entries.

Many SPs use DataCite DOIs and will thus be able to make use of DataCite Event Data to express explicit relations between entities with classification using the *relationType* metadata attribute (DataCite, 2024). However, global usage patterns of the various relation types may differ significantly. Since the relation types and their scope have not been strictly defined in the DataCite standard, a specific usage of a relation type may not be comparable with the way another infrastructure has implemented the relation in their metadata. For interoperability purposes, SPs are therefore encouraged to clearly document how they make use of DataCite Event Data.

Metadata expressing relations between datasets and other formal entities in a structured and machine-actionable way will support the creation and enrichment of scientific knowledge graphs (SKGs), such as GESIS Knowledge Graph³. By contributing to SKG development, SPs can enhance the visibility, interoperability, and reusability of their datasets, thereby supporting greater alignment with the FAIR principles.

Challenges persist with the clarity of hierarchical relationships among datasets, indicating a need for improved documentation or enhanced metadata practices to better visualize and understand these relationships. Responses show that some SPs provide hierarchical relations among datasets and subsets by employing PIDs, and some of the SPs also provide links not only with dataset versions but also with broader collections, series, or projects, demonstrating a nuanced approach to dataset management reflecting the complex nature of modern research data. However, more than half of the SPs do not provide hierarchical relations, leading to data management and utilization challenges. In addition, there is a noted lack of clarity on how hierarchical relationships are structured and connected among some SPs. Efforts are required to encourage the wider adoption and implementation of dataset hierarchies. Moreover, SPs should be encouraged to provide detailed documentation of dataset hierarchies and connections between datasets. Although Dataverse offers individual citations of files within a dataset through individual subset PIDs and include a data citation example for each file, not all SPs that use Dataverse have responded that they provide this. What a subset PID actually is and how this could be included in the data citation might therefore be difficult to interpret.

To summarise, one-third of SPs do not offer metadata that expresses relationships between data publications and other entities using machine-actionable PIDs. Enhancing connection between data publications and persistent identifiers for researchers, institutions and related FAIR Digital Objects improves FAIR principles and should therefore be a priority going forward. Efforts could also focus on providing hierarchical relationships among datasets and subsets and including subset PIDs in data citations. The need to cite data at different levels – specific subsets or broader conceptual levels (e.g., all rounds of a time series) – is apparent, and in need of further discussion.

Recommendation 8 – Raise awareness about data citation

Results from the survey

Regarding their awareness-raising activities, SPs were asked whether they provide information on how and why to cite data and whether they engage in national-level

³ <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/site/>

cooperation with organisations such as RPOs, RFOs, or journals to promote data citation.

In terms of guidance on *how* to cite data, many SPs reported that they provide a citation example for each dataset and include information on citing data within their terms of use. Only 7 SPs reported offering more detailed guidance: four through their websites or reports, and three by referring users to Dataverse information pages on data citation (Dataverse Project, n.d.). It also appears that this question was not fully understood by some SPs, which may have led to underreporting of guidance beyond citation examples.

Regarding guidance on *why* to cite data, 14 SPs reported providing some form of information, while 3 indicated that they do not. The nature of this information varies considerably, ranging from dedicated guides and documents on the importance of citing data, to links to Dataverse pages on data citation, to statements included in terms and conditions or user agreements. While some SPs offer comprehensive explanations emphasising that citing data is good scholarly practice, others provide only minimal information, such as a requirement to cite in order to access data or a simple citation example.

Lastly, with respect to engagement in national-level cooperation to promote data citation, 10 SPs reported participating in some form of collaboration, while 7 indicated that they do not. Among those involved, some cooperate directly with journals, editors, national funders, or research policymakers, while others promote data citation more broadly through national networks, projects, or research infrastructures.

Suggestions and reflections for enhancing current practices

The survey reveals some uneven practices: While most SPs provide basic citation examples, only a minority offer detailed guidance on how and why to cite data. In addition, national-level cooperation is inconsistent.

Because only some SPs offer more extensive information about why data citation is important, there is a need to raise greater awareness about citing data, and the CESSDA recommendations (Bornatici et al, 2025), in addition to the CESSDA webpage⁴ where these are presented to different stakeholders, will be beneficial moving forward. Therefore, efforts to promote data citation among stakeholders both nationally and internationally are needed.

Although the questionnaire did not explicitly address this issue, a further opportunity for promoting data citation lies in **encouraging data depositors themselves to cite their own datasets**. By providing guidance to depositors on self-citation practices,

⁴ <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Data-Citation-Guide>

SPs can support a broader cultural shift towards greater visibility and credit for data contributions in scholarly communication.

Conclusion

Data citation practices appear to be becoming more common in the daily workflow of CESSDA SPs, based on the 2024 survey on data citation practices among 19 CESSDA SPs and an additional review of their data sharing platforms in spring 2025. The findings highlight key strengths and areas for improvement across the CESSDA community. Overall, the responses demonstrate a strong commitment to supporting formal and consistent data citation practices, with most SPs making concerted efforts to align with CESSDA's recommendations.

At the same time, several areas of practice would benefit from further harmonisation and shared reflection. While awareness-raising and guidance materials for SP users are increasingly available, differences remain in how citation examples are presented and how key roles – such as data authors, creators or depositors – are labelled. Practices surrounding dataset versioning and the communication of version histories also vary, occasionally limiting clarity for users seeking to cite a specific version of a dataset. Broader implementation of PIDs and clearer documentation of dataset hierarchies would improve data traceability and linkage with other entities. Moreover, national-level cooperation and engagement with research-performing and research-funding organisations, journals, and other stakeholders appear uneven across SPs. Strengthening such partnerships would help consolidate a shared culture of recognition for data citation as a standard component of scholarly communication and embed it more firmly as a scholarly norm.

Looking ahead, while CESSDA SPs already demonstrate strong alignment with CESSDA's recommendations, further convergence in technical implementation and interoperability will be essential. Expanding support in areas such as automated version access, harmonised PID and metadata workflows, machine-readable citation export, and cross-stakeholder collaboration will consolidate CESSDA's role as a model for best practices in data citation management. These advancements would not only enhance citation accessibility and consistency but also enable greater interoperability, discoverability, and long-term traceability of European social science data.

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Appendix: Questionnaire

Recommendation 1: Request data to be cited

Q1.1

Does your SP request data to be cited?

If yes, please explain how it is done and, if available in English, provide a link to the document or webpage.

Recommendation 2: Provide all six core data citation components

Q2.1

Does the SP control the quality of the core components metadata provided by the data depositors, notably the dataset title?

Q2.2

Does the SP have the possibility to reserve a PID before publication?

Recommendation 3: Provide data citation suggestions including all six core components

Q3.1

Does your SP provide a data citation example per dataset?

If yes, please copy an example or provide a link to one example

Q3.2

If provided in different citation styles (e.g., APA, Chicago, MLA, etc.), please mention them.

Recommendation 4: Provide data versioning and access information

Q4.1

How is information about dataset versions and related changes provided to the users?

Q4.2

Does your SP provide access to metadata of all published versions of a dataset?

Q4.3

Does your SP provide access to older published versions of a dataset and how is it done?

Q4.4

How is information about the datasets that are no longer available provided to the users?

Recommendation 5: Facilitate data citation for authors through export and download of metadata for reference management software

Q5.1

Does your SP provide a tool to automatically import data citation components to a reference management software (e.g., Endnote, Mendeley and Zotero)?

Recommendation 6: Make citation information and other publication metadata accessible through generic structured metadata files

Q6.1

Does your SP provide metadata in a standardised and machine-actionable linked data format?

Recommendation 7: Make data publications and relations to other entities machine-actionable through rich metadata and PIDs

Q7.1

Does your SP provide metadata to express relationships between the data publications and other entities, using machine-actionable PIDs?

If yes, can you mention which PIDs (such as ORCID, ROR, etc.) are used to express relationships and what kind of entities and relations you use them for?

Q7.2

Does your SP provide hierarchical relations among datasets and subsets (such as dataset versions)?

If yes, please explain how this is done.

Q7.3

Does your SP facilitate the inclusion of subsets PIDs in the data citation?

If yes, please explain how this is done.

Recommendation 8: Raise awareness about data citation

Q8.1

Does your SP provide information on how to cite data?

If yes, please explain how and which users are targeted (data depositors and

end-users) and, if available in English, provide the links to the webpages or documents.

Q8.2

Does your SP provide information on why to cite data?

If yes, please explain how and which users are targeted (data depositors and end-users) and, if available in English, provide the links to the webpages or documents.

Q8.3

Does your SP engage in national-level cooperation (e.g., with RPO, RFO, journals, etc.) to promote data citation?

If so, please provide details.

Concluding remarks

Q9

The respondents could add any additional information and remarks.